

Corrigendum

Corrigendum: Stanchev R, Nikolov B (2025) Wetlands importance for the waterfowl species (order Anseriformes) wintering in Bulgaria, based on the Mid-Winter Waterbird Census data. Journal of the Bulgarian Geographical Society 52: 79–92. doi: 10.3897/jbgs.e144247

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Abstract

We recently published an assessment of the wetlands in Bulgaria important for the wintering waterfowl species (order Anseriformes) based on the Mid-Winter Waterbird Census data (Stanchev and Nikolov 2025). However, self-reevaluation of the data led to the refinement of some of the values used and species names. The changes given below do not affect the results and their discussion described in the publication.

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Corrigenda

- Table 1, page 83, column “Numerous waterfowl species”, rows 14 and 21: the English names of the species have been interchanged. To be read as Whooper Swan (*Cygnus cygnus*) on row 14 and Tundra Swan (*Cygnus columbianus*) on row 21.
- Table 1, column “Total counts / Total sites”, row 23 (Garganey (*Spatula querquedula*)), the correct number of total sites is 6 (not 7).
- Table 1, column “90% Winter population / sites”, row 1, the correct number of sites is 10 (not 9).
- Table 1, column “90% Winter population / sites”, row 2, the correct number of sites is 31 (not 30).
- Table 1, column “90% Winter population / sites”, row 3, the correct number of sites is 13 (not 12).
- Table 1, column “90% Winter population / sites”, row 5, the correct number of sites is 11 (not 28).
- Table 1, column “90% Winter population / sites”, row 8, the correct number of sites is 16 (not 41).
- Table 1, column “90% Winter population / sites”, in row 11, the correct number of sites is 5 (not 22).

- Table 1, column “90% Winter population / sites”, on row 14, the correct number of sites is 17 (not 18).
- Table 1, column “90% Winter population / sites”, on row 19, the correct number of sites is 11 (not 19).
- Table 1, column “90% Winter population / sites”, row 22, the correct number of sites is 11 (not 10).
- Table 1, column “90% Winter population / sites”, row 24, the correct number of sites is 8 (not 9).

The amended Table 1 is presented below:

Table 1. Numerous species of the order Anseriformes (more than 500 ind. in total, during the period 1977–2021), their total abundance, the total number of wintering sites, abundance in the most important wintering sites and the corresponding number of wintering sites and their conservation value. The “conservation value” parameter per species is indicated either as present (+) or absent (-). The “recorded in 2021” parameter indicates whether the species is present (+) or absent (-) in that year.

N	Numerous waterfowl species	Total counts / Total sites	90% Winter population / sites	Conservation value / recorded in 2021
1	Greater White-fronted Goose (<i>Anser albifrons</i>)	5434611 / 104	4937881 / 10	- / +
2	Mallard (<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>)	2495424 / 294	2271837 / 31	- / +
3	Common Pochard (<i>Aythya ferina</i>)	685801 / 111	656482 / 13	+ / +
4	Red-breasted Goose (<i>Branta ruficollis</i>)	559674 / 28	531080 / 3	+ / +
5	Tufted Duck (<i>Aythya fuligula</i>)	256516 / 70	233614 / 11	- / +
6	Common Teal (<i>Anas crecca</i>)	179137 / 188	161343 / 29	- / +
7	Common Shelduck (<i>Tadorna tadorna</i>)	110526 / 104	102676 / 2	+ / +
8	Eurasian Wigeon (<i>Mareca penelope</i>)	95165 / 123	85144 / 16	- / +
9	Northern Shoveler (<i>Spatula clypeata</i>)	74373 / 63	69039 / 3	- / +
10	Mute Swan (<i>Cygnus olor</i>)	46235 / 155	41741 / 30	+ / +
11	Northern Pintail (<i>Anas acuta</i>)	24113 / 67	22059 / 5	- / +
12	Greylag Goose (<i>Anser anser</i>)	19797 / 43	17263 / 8	+ / +
13	Red-breasted Merganser (<i>Mergus serrator</i>)	18629 / 39	16833 / 12	+ / +
14	Whooper Swan (<i>Cygnus cygnus</i>)	13977 / 75	12612 / 17	+ / +
15	Gadwall (<i>Mareca strepera</i>)	8238 / 91	7524 / 22	+ / +
16	Smew (<i>Mergellus albellus</i>)	7750 / 64	6981 / 16	+ / +
17	White-headed Duck (<i>Oxyura leucocephala</i>)	6127 / 10	6086 / 4	+ / +
18	Common Goldeneye (<i>Bucephala clangula</i>)	4937 / 50	4424 / 16	+ / +
19	Red-crested Pochard (<i>Netta rufina</i>)	4357 / 44	3886 / 11	+ / +
20	Goosander (<i>Mergus merganser</i>)	822 / 42	751 / 17	+ / +
21	Tundra Swan (<i>Cygnus columbianus</i>)	696 / 16	660 / 6	+ / +
22	Greater Scaup (<i>Aythya marila</i>)	640 / 24	583 / 11	+ / +
23	Garganey (<i>Spatula querquedula</i>)	583 / 6	550 / 2	+ / -
24	Ruddy Shelduck (<i>Tadorna ferruginea</i>)	578 / 33	520 / 8	+ / +

- Table 2, page 84, column “Total counts / Total sites”, row 5 (Bean Goose (*Anser fabalis*)), the correct total count is 80 (not 74).
The amended Table 2 is presented below:

Table 2. Rare waterfowl species (less than 500 ind. in total, during the period 1977–2021, the total number of wintering sites and their conservation value. The “conservation value” parameter per species is indicated either as present (+) or absent (-). The “recorded in 2021” parameter indicates whether the species is present (+) or absent (-) in that year.

N	Rare waterfowl species	Total counts / Total sites	Conservation value / recorded in 2021
1	Ferruginous Duck (<i>Aythya nyroca</i>)	402 / 39	+ / +
2	Common Eider (<i>Somateria mollissima</i>)	130 / 14	+ / +
3	Velvet Scoter (<i>Melanitta fusca</i>)	111 / 18	+ / -
4	Long-tailed Duck (<i>Clangula hyemalis</i>)	106 / 8	+ / -
5	Bean Goose (<i>Anser fabalis</i>)	80 / 10	+ / -
6	Common Scoter (<i>Melanitta nigra</i>)	64 / 10	+ / -
7	Lesser White-fronted Goose (<i>Anser erythropus</i>)	10 / 7	+ / -
8	Barnacle Goose (<i>Branta leucopsis</i>)	2 / 2	+ / -

References

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: RHS. Data curation: BN. Supervision: BN. Visualization: RHS. Writing - original draft: RHS. Writing - review and editing: BN.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.